

Beyond Textbooks: Technological Barriers to Entrepreneurship Programs in Tanzania Secondary Schools

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Abstract: Technology plays a pivotal role in modern education, offering diverse opportunities for enhancing teaching and learning experiences. However, in many developing countries the integration of technology into entrepreneurship programs in secondary schools faces significant barriers. This study investigates the technological challenges hindering entrepreneurship education in Tanzania secondary schools, employing a qualitative approach to explore the perspectives of key stakeholders including heads of schools, teachers, and students who were selected purposively. The interview, focus group discussion, and document analysis were used to collect data finally thematic approach helped to analyze them. Findings reveal pervasive deficiencies in technological resources, including unreliable power supply, inadequate maintenance of equipment, and limitations in school facilities to support technology-based learning. Furthermore, the current curriculum lacks adequate coverage of modern entrepreneurial practices and digital learning tools, such as e-commerce and digital marketing strategies. These challenges impede students' ability to develop practical skills essential for success in the digital economy. The study recommends collaboration between government agencies, educational institutions, and the private sector. Also, comprehensive infrastructure development, curriculum reform, and investment in teacher training programs to address these challenges. By overcoming technological barriers, Tanzanian secondary schools can create conducive environments for practical entrepreneurship education, empowering students with the skills needed for economic empowerment and innovation.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship education, Technology integration, Secondary schools, Tanzanian

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Introduction

The need for entrepreneurship education has become widely recognized as an important part of secondary school programs worldwide, and the main objective of it is to impart students with the necessary skills and knowledge needed for them to cope with the 21st-century economy. In Tanzania and many developing countries at large, secondary school courses are now created to include entrepreneurship education is seen as a way of expanding economic development, empowering youth, and solving the unemployment challenge (Du Toit & Ntimbwa, 2023). However, the challenges

exist not only in the incorporation of the technology but also in the implementation of entrepreneurship programs in the case of Tanzanian secondary schools. Tanzania in as much as it tries to improve its education access and quality still struggles with infrastructural and resource constraints that hamper the delivery of entrepreneurship education (URT, 2019). Secondary schools in Tanzania are technologically underserved because of the lack of hardware such as computers, poor internet connection, and essential software applications. The lack of these resources may hamper not only the strategies to satisfy the students' educational requirements of entrepreneurship but also the opportunities for students to be trained in real-life business transactions (Soi & Mkulu, 2022).

Integrating technology in entrepreneurship education is pivotal in providing students with hands-on experiences, fostering creativity, and developing critical thinking skills (Xiong et al., 2023). However, the scarcity of technological resources in Tanzanian secondary schools presents a significant barrier to adopting innovative pedagogical approaches that could enhance the effectiveness of entrepreneurship programs. Furthermore, the pedagogical methods employed in Tanzanian secondary schools may not fully align with the practical nature of entrepreneurship education (Alawi et al., 2022). Traditional textbook-centric approaches prevail due to the limited availability of technology and the lack of teacher training in utilizing digital resources effectively. Consequently, students may not have sufficient opportunities to engage in experiential learning, collaborate on entrepreneurial projects, or develop skills such as problem-solving and teamwork, which are essential for entrepreneurial success (Samwel Mwasalwiba, 2010). An in-depth investigation of the perspectives of stakeholders intimately associated with the initiatives is necessary to understand the specific technological barriers preventing Tanzanian secondary school entrepreneurship programs from succeeding. Initiatives for entrepreneurial education are supported by educators, learners, and administrators such as academics, managers, and policymakers. Their viewpoints are extremely important for policy development and practices because they highlight the restrictions imposed by technological limitations and offer proactive solutions for managing and getting over these roadblocks. Limited access to technology in educational settings is a recognized issue in developing countries, particularly Tanzania. This lack of resources can hinder the effective implementation of various education programs, and entrepreneurship education is no exception (Kapinga, 2017).

While textbooks may provide a basic foundation, technology offers a dynamic and interactive learning environment for entrepreneurship education. Since it allows for exposure to real-world tools and platforms for students to become modern entrepreneurs, they have to learn how to use and understand business software, internet marketing tools, and e-commerce platforms. Furthermore, developing essential digital skills in entrepreneurship programs can equip students with vital digital literacy skills such as data analysis, online communication, and social media marketing. In addition, technology allows for simulations, online resources, and collaborative learning platforms that foster creativity, problem-solving, and teamwork – all crucial aspects of entrepreneurial ventures. Therefore, this qualitative study addresses the following objectives: First, identify the specific technological resources that are most lacking in Tanzanian secondary schools and how these deficiencies hinder entrepreneurship education. Second to examine the pedagogical approaches used in these programs and how limited technology restricts the development of essential entrepreneurial skills. The last is to investigate the perspectives of key stakeholders, including teachers, students, and administrators, on the challenges posed by technological limitations and their suggestions for overcoming these barriers. This study intends to provide important insights for stakeholders, educators, and policymakers striving to promote entrepreneurship education in Tanzanian secondary schools by identifying specific technology constraints and their influence on pedagogy and skill development.

Literature review

Status Quo of Policies and Initiatives for Entrepreneurship Education

Bore et al., (2023) argued that entrepreneurship is known to play a critical role in fostering creative thinking, innovation, financial stability, and economic advancement. Therefore, it has been incorporated into secondary school curricula in nations worldwide. In advanced economies such as Finland, entrepreneurship education in basic education programs

emphasizes practical application while integrating entrepreneurial principles across many curricula (Carayannis et al., 2020). Also, to help children develop entrepreneurial abilities, the “Network for Teaching Entrepreneurship (NFTE)” in the US provides extensive curriculum materials and teacher training (Nakamoto & Rice, 2017). Besides, recognizing the need to promote entrepreneurial thinking for economic development, developing countries have adopted a wide range of policies and initiatives. In Malaysia for example, the “National Entrepreneurship Education Blueprint” focuses on experiential learning, mentorship, and industry partnerships to ensure that students acquire practical skills (Ahmad, 2013). Similarly, Brazil’s young entrepreneur program promotes partnerships between schools and local communities (companies) and provides practical lessons to students (Stadler et al., 2022). These programs demonstrate the flexibility of entrepreneurship education in various socio-economic settings. However, the field of entrepreneurship education is still in the infancy stage in developing nations, but it shows signs of expansion throughout Africa. The “Schools Act” for example in South Africa promotes collaborations with nearby companies and highlights the inclusion of entrepreneurship in the curriculum (Department of Basic Education, 2011). The Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004 stated that the “National Policy on Education” in Nigeria acknowledges entrepreneurship as a crucial aspect of education and encourages collaborations between educational institutions and business sectors (Bakar et al., 2015).

In the context of Tanzania, the need for entrepreneurship education is reflected in policies like the “Education and Training Policy” as well as the “National Five-Year Development Plan” (URT, 2014). Initiatives such as the “Youth Entrepreneurship Scheme” aim to financially support young entrepreneurs (Musa et al., 2022). However, despite these efforts, challenges persist in translating policies into effective classroom practices. In July 2023, the government of Tanzania initiated a new educational policy effective in early 2024, reflecting the needs of the current world of which entrepreneurship is among them. Therefore, Tanzania’s Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology has introduced some policy measures to integrate entrepreneurship education into the regular curriculum (URT, 2022). Classes in business and entrepreneurship have been scheduled to prepare students with a mindset and skills conducive to entrepreneurship and practical knowledge. In terms of economic growth, employment creation, and the overall uplift of Tanzanian youth, this policy initiative recognizes the value of entrepreneurial education (URT, 2022). When we examine the importance of EE at the Tanzanian public secondary school level today and judge what it might look like in the future, the impact of these policies becomes fundamental. It is crucial to recognize that context matters regarding entrepreneurship education are not the same worldwide, therefore, it is not always possible to adopt global approaches immediately. Because every nation has different potentials and challenges, each must choose a strategy relevant to its socioeconomic and cultural setting (Alain et al., 2019). Therefore, adaptation is necessary to guarantee that EE meets regional requirements and objectives (Du Toit & Ntimbwa, 2023). However, certain general concepts may be relevant to everyone, we must thus critically evaluate international trends and methods in light of their adaptation to Tanzania’s educational environment as we investigate approaches to advancing EE in Tanzanian public secondary schools. Generally, the global analysis of entrepreneurship education policy reveals various strategies, from the established systems of powerful nations to the innovative methods of developing countries. Tanzania has laid the foundation for entrepreneurial education; nevertheless, addressing the unique contextual difficulties that emerge in its educational setting is required to turn policies into effective implementations. By learning from global experiences and tailoring strategies to local conditions, Tanzania, may increase the efficacy of its entrepreneurship education programs and ensure that the youth has the skills required for economic engagement and creativity.

Limitations and Solutions for Implementing Entrepreneurship Education in Secondary Schools

Despite strong foundations, the application of entrepreneurship education is difficult in developed nations. The unwillingness of existing educational systems to adapt is one ongoing issue. One recurring problem in nations like the US, where entrepreneurship education is well-established, is making sure that teachers have the pedagogical abilities

needed to present entrepreneurial information engagingly (Kuratko, 2017). Strategies set to address this situation frequently entail specialized teacher training programs and partnerships with business leaders to close the knowledge gap between theory and practice. Apart from developed nations, developing nations have unique difficulties when attempting to provide entrepreneurial education. Lack of resources, including appropriate teaching materials and skilled instructors, is a prevalent problem. For example, in India, where entrepreneurship education is becoming more popular, a lack of resources frequently results in a curriculum with insufficient breadth and depth (UNCTAD, 2011). Public-private partnerships are one type of strategy used to increase program sustainability and the availability of resources in most developing nations.

Across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), implementing entrepreneurship education in secondary schools encounters multifaceted challenges. One prevalent issue is the misalignment between curricular content and the needs of the local job market. This discrepancy can lead to a mismatch between skills acquired through entrepreneurship education and the demands of the economy (Mbunda & Kapinga, 2021). Strategies taken to address this challenge in SSA involve regular curriculum reviews to ensure relevance and close collaboration with industry players for up-to-date insights. Insufficient infrastructure in many SSA nations makes implementation more difficult. The integration of digital tools in entrepreneurship education is impeded by limited access to technology and internet connectivity, which limits students' exposure to modern business methods (Jones et al., 2018). Initiatives to improve digital literacy and focused investments in infrastructure development are strategies taken to address digital gaps in teaching and learning entrepreneurship education and other subjects.

Besides, socio-cultural perceptions of entrepreneurship also present challenges. In some SSA societies, entrepreneurship might be viewed as a less prestigious career path than traditional professions. This perception can influence students' interest and engagement with entrepreneurship education (African Development Bank (AfDB), 2022). Strategies involve targeted awareness campaigns to shift cultural attitudes and highlight the value of entrepreneurial endeavors. In addition, the lack of teacher entrepreneurship pedagogy training is a persistent problem throughout SSA. Educators may lack the skills necessary to provide hands-on, experiential learning, which would reduce the value of entrepreneurship education (Jones et al., 2018). Teacher training programs are included in strategies frequently made possible by collaborations with academic institutions and business leaders. Generally, the challenges in implementing entrepreneurship education in secondary schools, span across global, regional, and local contexts. From the resistance to change in developed nations to the resource constraints in developing countries and the nuanced challenges within SSA, each setting presents a unique set of obstacles. Strategies for overcoming these challenges often require a multifaceted approach, combining targeted teacher training, infrastructure development, cultural awareness initiatives, and collaboration with industry stakeholders. The global discourse on entrepreneurship education reveals both the shared struggles and the contextual nuances that influence the success of these programs. Learning from the strategies implemented worldwide can inform more effective approaches in Sub-Saharan Africa and contribute to the continuous refinement of entrepreneurship education initiatives globally.

Research Methodology

The study was conducted in Tanzania's eastern region in the Morogoro Municipality. Given that Morogoro Municipality is easily accessible and typical of the country, it was selected as the research area to shed light on the difficulties faced by secondary schools in urban settings. A qualitative research approach was employed to comprehensively explore the technological barriers hindering entrepreneurship programs in Tanzanian secondary schools. Mayoux, (2006) argues that qualitative research allows for an in-depth understanding of complex phenomena. Therefore, it helped capture the intricate perspectives and experiences of key stakeholders involved in entrepreneurship education. The study adopted a case study design, focusing on multiple secondary schools within Morogoro Municipality. According to Aberdeen, (2013), a case study design offers the flexibility to investigate a phenomenon within its real-life context. Hence

this allows for an in-depth exploration of the specific technological barriers and their impacts on entrepreneurship education in Tanzanian secondary schools. Both primary and secondary sources of data were utilized in this study. Primary data were collected directly from key stakeholders involved in entrepreneurship education, including headteachers, teachers, and students. Secondary data sources such as educational policies, curriculum documents, and previous research provided additional context and background information.

Furthermore, Purposive sampling was used to select participants from Morogoro Municipality secondary schools, including headteachers, teachers, and students, based on their experience and involvement in entrepreneurship education. The study utilized semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs), and document analysis to gather data on participants' perspectives, experiences, and opinions. The analysis also included reviewing relevant educational documents to supplement and triangulate the findings. The study employed thematic analysis to analyze qualitative data, systematically identifying and interpreting patterns or themes within the data. This involved coding, grouping codes into themes, and interpreting their meanings and implications about research objectives as proposed by Braun & Clarke, (2006).

Findings and Discussions

Limited Access to Technology

The study's findings revealed that limited access to technology significantly hampers entrepreneurship education in Tanzanian secondary schools. For instance, many schools lacked computers and internet connectivity, hindering students' ability to engage in online research, access relevant entrepreneurship resources, and develop digital literacy skills. Moreover, outdated or insufficient software and hardware limited the implementation of innovative pedagogical approaches, such as simulation exercises or business planning software, which are essential for fostering practical entrepreneurial skills among students. Some heads of schools emphasized the critical nature of technology access in school, stating:

"Without adequate computers and internet, our students miss out on vital resources for entrepreneurship education, hindering their development of essential skills for the future."

Furthermore, a teacher highlighted the impact of limited technology on teaching entrepreneurship in commerce subject, commented:

"The lack of computers and internet connectivity is a major problem in my school. It is challenging to demonstrate real-world scenarios or utilize online tools effectively, limiting students' understanding and engagement in commerce-related entrepreneurship concepts."

During the discussion, teachers also expressed concern over the lack of technology hindering effective teaching methods, stating:

"Without proper access to technology, our ability to provide hands-on experiences and practical learning opportunities in entrepreneurship is severely restricted, impacting students' preparedness for the contemporary economic circumstances."

The respondents' comments highlight how difficult it is for Tanzanian secondary schools to provide enough technology access, which hinders both students' educational opportunities and instructors' capacity to teach entrepreneurship. The findings are in line with what was identified by (Soi & Mkulu, 2022) who asserted that this problem undermines Tanzanian youth's capacity for economic empowerment and creativity and reflects a larger systemic problem that hinders the acquisition of critical entrepreneurial skills. The issue of limited technology access in Tanzanian secondary schools poses a critical barrier to effective entrepreneurship education. Without adequate as well as modern technological resources, students are deprived of essential digital literacy skills and real-world entrepreneurial experiences (Zupan et al., 2018) Furthermore, teachers struggle to implement innovative pedagogical approaches, hindering the development

of practical entrepreneurial skills (Van Gelderen, 2023). While initiatives such as the Tanzanian Education Sector Analysis have highlighted the need for improved curriculum, infrastructure, and resources in Tanzania secondary schools to create independent graduates with self-employment skills (URT, 2019, 2022) progress remains slow. Addressing this issue requires concerted efforts from policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to prioritize investment in education, particularly in technology infrastructure and teacher training. Failure to address these technological deficiencies risks perpetuating the cycle of unemployment and economic stagnation among Tanzanian youth, limiting their ability to thrive in an increasingly digital and entrepreneurial global economy.

Gaps in Digital Literacy

The study revealed significant gaps in digital literacy among both teachers and students in Tanzanian secondary schools. Teachers struggled to effectively integrate technology into entrepreneurship education due to limited training and familiarity with digital tools. For example, some teachers expressed difficulty in navigating software applications for business simulations or online research. Similarly, students exhibited varying levels of digital proficiency, with many lacking basic skills such as internet browsing or word processing. This lack of digital literacy impedes students' ability to leverage technology for entrepreneurial learning and limits their readiness for participation in the digital economy. Below are some quotes that highlight these viewpoints:

"I recognize the challenge of lacking expert teachers in digital literacy and limited opportunities for professional development. This impacts our ability to effectively integrate technology into entrepreneurship education, hindering students' preparedness for the digital economy" (Interview with head of school).

"I find that my limited digital skills do not align with the demands of modern technology in entrepreneurship education. This hampers my effectiveness in delivering comprehensive and engaging lessons to students" (Interview with teacher).

"My low level of proficiency in digital skills significantly hinders my ability to effectively utilize technology for entrepreneurial learning. This limits my opportunities for acquiring essential skills and competencies for future success in the digital economy" (Interview with student).

These findings highlight pervasive gaps in digital literacy among both teachers and students in Tanzanian secondary schools, posing a significant barrier to effective entrepreneurship education. This overarching issue reflects systemic challenges in providing adequate training and resources to facilitate the integration of technology into the curriculum, ultimately impacting students' preparedness for the demands of the modern digital economy.

Significant disparities in digital literacy between instructors and pupils in Tanzanian secondary schools are a worldwide problem shared by many developing and even rich nations. Studies show that teachers' insufficient knowledge of digital literacy impedes the successful incorporation of technology into educational programs (Al-Lawati et al., 2022; Alawi et al., 2022). Similarly, students' incapacity to use technology for learning and future employment opportunities is hindered by their low level of digital competency (OECD, 2015). In a worldwide scenario, countries such as Finland and South Korea have made substantial investments in teacher training programs to enhance digital literacy skills (OECD, 2015). These initiatives have been crucial in equipping educators with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively utilize technology in the classroom. However, challenges persist in ensuring equitable access to training opportunities for all educators, particularly in resource-constrained contexts like Tanzania. According to Mark West et al., (2019). The digital gap contributes to already-existing educational inequality, impeding socio-economic growth and global competitiveness. Governments, academic institutions, and international organizations must work together to address the problem by offering teachers and students thorough training in digital literacy. If these gaps are not closed, inequality may continue and young people's opportunities to prosper in the increasingly digitalized global economy may be restricted.

Insufficient Curriculum and Resources for Modern Technology

The study revealed the inadequacy of the current curriculum and resources for technology-driven entrepreneurship education in Tanzanian secondary schools. Existing materials often lack relevance to modern entrepreneurial practices and fail to integrate digital learning tools. Under document analysis, the study revealed that Tanzanian secondary schools' current curriculum, syllabus, and scheme of work lack adequate coverage of topics relevant to modern entrepreneurship, such as e-commerce and digital marketing strategies. Moreover, the limited availability of online resources and software specifically tailored for entrepreneurship programs hinders students' ability to develop practical skills essential for success in the digital economy, such as business planning and financial management using specialized software. Some remarks from the quotes below serve as illustrations:

"I saw directly how our programs are impacted by the inadequate curriculum and resources for technology-driven entrepreneurship education. For instance, students lack critical abilities for the modern corporate environment if e-commerce and digital marketing are not covered" (Interview with head of school).

"I feel uncomfortable by the lack of required skills due to inadequate curriculum and resources. Without access to modern entrepreneurship topics and digital learning tools, our preparedness for the digital economy is compromised" (interview with economics student).

During discussions, teachers also lamented the ongoing trend of insufficient coverage of modern entrepreneurship topics and the absence of specialized software in the curriculum. They commented:

"Continual lack of coverage on modern entrepreneurship topics in the curriculum leaves students ill-prepared for the evolving corporate environment. Also, the absence of specialized software limits students' practical skill development crucial for success in the digital economy".

These results highlight the structural problem of inadequate curriculum and resources for teaching technology-driven entrepreneurship in Tanzanian secondary schools. This deficiency makes pupils less prepared for the digital economy since the curriculum does not include digital learning resources and contemporary entrepreneurial activities. In another study by Alawi et al., (2022) similar findings were reported, indicating a lack of integration of modern entrepreneurial practices and digital learning tools in the curriculum of Tanzania secondary schools, particularly in Zanzibar.

The results highlight a structural problem with Tanzanian secondary schools' weak curricula and insufficient resources for teaching technology-driven entrepreneurship. This shortcoming represents a larger worldwide issue in addition to impeding students' readiness for the digital economy. Research reveals similar problems in Indian educational institutions by Roy & Mukherjee, (2017) showing that an antiquated curriculum and a shortage of digital tools hamper students' capacity to learn contemporary entrepreneurial skills. In addition, Pittaway, (2021) study conducted in the US shows differences in entrepreneurship education, with underrepresented populations needing help accessing pertinent technologies and curricula. These findings emphasize the need for comprehensive reform in educational systems in Tanzania to ensure that curriculum and resources align with the demands of the digital age. Without addressing these structural deficiencies, students will continue to be ill-prepared for the evolving corporate landscape, perpetuating inequalities in access to entrepreneurial opportunities and economic advancement.

Challenges related to infrastructure

The study identified challenges related to infrastructure in Tanzanian secondary schools, including unreliable power supply, inadequate maintenance of existing equipment, and limitations in school facilities to support technology-based learning. For instance, frequent power outages disrupt classroom activities reliant on technology, while poorly maintained computers and internet connectivity issues hinder effective teaching and learning. Similarly, insufficient infrastructure such as overcrowded classrooms and inadequate facilities for computer labs restrict students' access to technology-based learning opportunities. These infrastructure challenges reflect broader systemic issues that impede the

integration of technology into education eventually limiting effective practical teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education. The following quotations illustrate these points of view:

“The absence of practical skills due to infrastructural issues bothers most of us especially those who take business subjects. We are forced to rely heavily on theoretical learning because of unreliable power supply and inadequate facilities for technology-based learning, hindering our preparation for real-world entrepreneurship endeavors” (Interview with student).

“I have been working as a principal for many years now, I witness the extent of infrastructure challenges daily. For instance, power outages disrupt classes using technology, hindering our entrepreneurship programs” (Interview with head of school).

She added:

“Poorly maintained equipment and overcrowded classrooms, especially after the free educational policy limit students’ access to technology-based learning opportunities, impacting their overall educational experience”.

The same claim is explained by teachers during discussions, they express how infrastructure challenges critically affect the teaching and learning process. Commenting:

“Frequent power outages disrupt lesson delivery, while overcrowded classrooms limit student engagement in technology-based activities. These challenges impede the effective teaching of entrepreneurship education, hindering students’ practical skill development” (Discussion with teachers).

This indicates that although the problem of infrastructure existed in the past, the policy of free education has been a stimulus due to the increase in the number of students who are not compatible with the available resources. These findings are in line with Kapinga, (2017; Shukia, (2020) who states that the implementation of the free education policy in Tanzania has led to overcrowding in classrooms as more students enroll in schools, exceeding the capacity of existing facilities. This influx of students strains resources, resulting in insufficient infrastructure, such as inadequate classroom space, limited supplies, and insufficient equipment, thereby impeding effective teaching and learning experiences. The study’s results on infrastructural constraints show how Tanzania’s free education policy has put a burden on available resources. Growing enrollment has resulted in overcrowded classrooms and restricted access to technology, impeding the ability of entrepreneurship programs to offer hands-on learning experiences and this poses a significant barrier (Shukia, 2020). Frequent power outages, as mentioned by the head of school and student interviewee, disrupt technology-dependent lessons. Overcrowded classrooms, as noted by teachers, restrict student engagement with technology-based activities. Baiden et al., (2018) argue that lack of practical experience can leave students unprepared for real-world entrepreneurial endeavors, limiting the effectiveness of the program. The free education policy’s positive goal of increased access to education is commendable. However, its success hinges on adequate infrastructure development. Without sufficient classrooms, well-maintained equipment, and reliable power, effective technology integration remains elusive. This calls for a multi-pronged approach. Upgrading school infrastructure, including proper maintenance of existing equipment, is crucial. Additionally, exploring alternative power sources like solar panels could mitigate the impact of unreliable electricity.

Implications/Recommendations for the Practice and Conclusion

Recommendations from International Best Practices within Tanzania’s Context

Drawing from international best practices and considering Tanzania’s context, several recommendations can be made to address the challenges identified in Tanzanian secondary schools. Firstly, there is a need for comprehensive infrastructure development, including expanding school facilities, improving power supply reliability, and enhancing internet connectivity. Secondly, curriculum reform is essential to integrate modern entrepreneurial practices and digital learning tools into entrepreneurship education. This should include coverage of topics like e-commerce and digital marketing strategies. Thirdly, investment in teacher training programs is crucial to equip educators with the skills to

effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. Lastly, collaboration between government agencies, educational institutions, and private sector stakeholders can facilitate the provision of necessary resources and support for entrepreneurship education initiatives. By implementing these recommendations, Tanzania can create a conducive environment for practical entrepreneurship education, empowering students with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in the digital economy.

Study's implications for practice

This study on technological barriers in Tanzanian secondary school entrepreneurship programs holds significant value. Exploring challenges faced by heads of schools, teachers, and students, sheds light on the gap between traditional textbook learning and the practical needs of aspiring entrepreneurs. Identifying limitations in access to technology, digital literacy, curriculum resources, and infrastructure paves the way for targeted improvements. These findings can inform policymakers, educators, and NGOs in developing effective strategies to equip students with the technological skills and knowledge crucial for success in today's entrepreneurial ventures. Ultimately, this study contributes to fostering a more robust and technology-driven approach to entrepreneurship education in Tanzania and other developing countries.

Conclusion

The study sheds light on the challenges related to infrastructure and curriculum deficiencies hindering effective entrepreneurship education in Tanzanian secondary schools. The findings underscore the critical need for comprehensive reforms to address these systemic issues. Improving infrastructure, including reliable power supply and adequate facilities, is paramount for creating conducive learning environments. Additionally, curriculum reform is necessary to integrate modern entrepreneurial practices and digital learning tools into entrepreneurship education. Moreover, investing in teacher training programs is crucial to ensure educators are equipped to effectively utilize technology in their teaching practices. By implementing these recommendations, Tanzania can create a conducive environment for practical entrepreneurship education, empowering students with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in the digital economy. Ultimately, addressing these challenges holds significant implications for students' academic and professional development, contributing to economic growth and social development in Tanzania.

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